

Oxidation of isoniazid and glutathione with bromamine-T

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Bromamine-T oxidizes isoniazid and glutathione stoichiometrically in pH 5 acetate buffer medium with four- and ten-electron change, respectively. Back-titration procedures have been developed for the determination of isoniazid and glutathione. The methods have been successfully employed for the determination of isoniazid in pharmaceutical preparations and also for the estimation of metal complexes of glutathione. A direct titration for the determination of glutathione with a visual end-point is developed involving a one-electron change corresponding to the oxidation of thiol group to disulfide.

Bromamine-T (BAT) has received considerable attention as an oxidimetric reagent^{1,2}. The oxidation of glutamic acid and its rare earth complexes with BAT is reported³. Microestimation of some hydrazine derivatives in sulfuric acid medium have been studied⁴. Some thiols have been determined by direct titration with BAT⁵. Many kinetic investigations with BAT have been reported⁶. The conductometric interaction of BAT with some metal ions has been studied⁷. The conductance behavior of BAT has been studied as a function of temperature in different composition of water-methanol and water-ethanol (v/v)⁸. Recently, we have reported the photolysis of aqueous solution of BAT⁹. A survey of literature reveals that the oxidimetric determination of isoniazid and glutathione with BAT have not been reported.

Pyridine-4-carboxylic acid hydrazide (isoniazid, INH), an antitubercular drug, is now widely used together with rifampicin and streptomycin for the chemotherapy of tuberculosis. Glutathione (GSH) is a tripeptide (glutamylcysteinylglycine) and its importance in mammals system is believed to be related to its function in oxidative metabolism and detoxication¹⁰. In view of the importance of the above compounds and also in continuation of our work on aromatic sulfonyl haloamines, we report back-titration procedures for the determination of INH and GSH with BAT in pH 5 acetate buffer medium. A direct titration procedure for the determination of GSH with BAT is also described. The methods have been extended to the determination of INH in pharmaceutical preparations and also for the determination of metal complexes of glutathione.

Results and Discussion

The reactions were studied in various media. Smooth stoichiometric oxidation occurred in pH 5 buffer medium. The data on the extent of oxidation of isoniazid and glutathione with BAT in various media for a particular interval of time is given in Table 1. The stoichiometric oxida-

tion of the silver and cadmium complexes of glutathione by bromamine-T takes place in 15 min in pH 5 acetate buffer medium. Results for the estimation of INH, GSH and metal complexes of GSH by back-titration method are shown in Table 2. Results of direct titration of GSH and its metal complexes with visual end-point are given in Table 3. Table 4 shows the results of determination of INH in various pharmaceutical preparations.

Table 1. Extent of oxidation of isoniazid and glutathione in various media

Time = 15 min, BAT taken=2.5 mmol, substrate taken = 0.04 mmol, temp = 30°

Medium	mmol of BAT consumed mmol of substrate taken	
	Isoniazid	Glutathione
pH 1	2.401	5.692
pH 2	2.116	5.267
pH 3	2.339	5.522
pH 4	2.339	5.607
pH 5	2.005	5.010
pH 6	2.005	4.757
pH 8	1.726	3.908
pH 9	1.949	4.842
HCl*	2.450	5.352
HClO ₄ *	2.228	6.117
H ₂ SO ₄ *	2.395	4.842
NaOH*	1.838	3.823

*0.1 mol dm⁻³ overall concentration in the reaction mixture.

The stoichiometry of oxidation of INH with BAT can be represented as

where R is CH₃-C₆H₄SO₂. The presence of isonicotinic acid in the reaction mixture was indicated by its colour reaction with sodium pentacyanoammine ferrous¹¹. Paper chromatography was used to identify *p*-toluenesulfonamide (R_f = 0.905). Benzyl alcohol saturated with water used as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin, 1% HCl in ethanol as the spray reagent.

Table 2. Estimation of isoniazid, glutathione and metal complexes of glutathione with bromamine-T (back-titration)*

Time = 15 min, medium : pH 5 acetate buffer

Isoniazid			Glutathione			Metal complexes of glutathione					
Taken mg	Found mg	Standard deviation	Taken mg	Found mg	Standard deviation	Ag			Cd		
						Taken mg	Found mg	Standard deviation	Taken mg	Found mg	Standard deviation
2.14	2.09	0.02	3.14	3.20	0.02	3.45	3.48	0.02	4.02	3.98	0.01
4.28	4.23	0.01	6.28	6.33	0.02	6.90	6.84	0.03	8.04	8.00	0.02
6.42	6.48	0.03	9.42	9.36	0.03	10.35	10.31	0.03	12.06	12.09	0.02
8.56	8.50	0.03	12.56	12.60	0.01	13.80	13.83	0.02	16.08	16.10	0.02
10.70	10.74	0.01	15.70	15.74	0.04	17.25	17.21	0.03	18.09	18.06	0.03
12.84	12.77	0.01	18.84	18.79	0.03	20.70	20.75	0.03	20.10	20.09	0.02
14.98	15.06	0.02	21.98	21.92	0.04	24.15	24.11	0.03	22.11	22.11	0.01
17.12	17.05	0.03	25.12	25.17	0.04	27.60	27.65	0.04	24.12	24.14	0.02

*Average of six determinations.

Table 3. Estimation of glutathione and metal complexes of glutathione with bromamine-T by direct titration, with a visual end-point*

Glutathione			Metal complexes of glutathione					
Taken mg	Found mg	Standard deviation	Ag			Cd		
			Taken mg	Found mg	Standard deviation	Taken mg	Found mg	Standard deviation
5.86	5.84	0.02	5.74	5.77	0.02	4.92	4.88	0.03
11.72	11.75	0.02	11.48	11.50	0.02	9.84	9.81	0.03
17.58	17.62	0.03	17.22	17.19	0.02	14.76	14.79	0.02
23.44	23.43	0.02	22.96	22.90	0.03	19.68	19.71	0.02
29.30	29.26	0.03	28.70	28.69	0.02	24.60	24.56	0.03
35.16	35.21	0.04	34.44	34.46	0.03	29.52	29.48	0.02
41.02	41.05	0.02	40.18	40.21	0.03	34.44	34.49	0.03
46.88	46.82	0.02	45.92	45.88	0.03	39.36	39.40	0.02
52.74	52.76	0.02	51.66	51.63	0.02	44.28	44.25	0.02
58.60	58.57	0.03	57.40	57.44	0.03	49.20	49.18	0.02

*Calculations based on consumption of one equivalent of oxidant per mole of substrate; average of six determinations.

Table 4. Determination of isoniazid in pharmaceutical preparations with bromamine-T

Sample	Label	Amount of isoniazid per tablet (mg) or per ml of syrup (mg), Recovery ± SD*	
		Proposed method	Spectrophotometric method ^a
Tablet :			
Isokin (Warner)	100	98 ± 0.6	99 ± 0.68
Isonex (Pfizer)	100	98 ± 0.6	101 ± 0.54
	300	298 ± 0.58	297 ± 0.62
Solonex (Macleods)	100	97 ± 0.6	98 ± 0.6
	300	297 ± 0.65	296 ± 0.55
Syrup :			
Isokin (Warner)	20	20.1 ± 0.70	20.5 ± 0.75

*Average of six determinations. ^aRef. 17.

A direct titration of INH with BAT was not feasible. as the reaction was slow. The direct titration of glutathione involves one-electron change which can be represented as

where G is $\text{HOOC-CH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CONH}$

The presence of disulfide (GSSG) in the reaction products was detected by paper chromatography, with phenol saturated with water as solvent and ninhydrin as spray reagent¹². Variation in the amount of KI or H₂SO₄ did not affect the results in the direct titration. Attempts to carry out potentiometric titrations of GSH with BAT were unsuccessful, as there was no potential jump at the equivalence point.

The back-titration results of the GSH with BAT show that the oxidation takes place with a ten-electron change to the aldehydic stage. The reaction can be represented as

where G' is $\text{HOOC-CH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CONH}$

The aldehyde peptide formed was detected¹³ in the reaction mixture. The stoichiometry observed for the metal complexes of GSH in direct and back-titration methods are similar to reactions (2) and (3). The order of addition of INH/GSH and BAT did not affect the stoichiometry.

The behavior of BAT is similar to chloramine-T¹⁴ and bromamine-B¹⁵. The possible oxidizing species in acidified BAT solution are RNHBr, RNBr₂ and HOBr. Therefore, any one of these three species may be responsible for the oxidation of the substrates in the back-titrations under the present experimental conditions. The rapid rate of oxidation around pH 4–6 can probably be attributed to the rapid disproportionation of RNHBr in acidified BAT solution to RNH₂ and RNBr₂ around this pH, as suggested by Higuchi *et al.*¹⁶.

In the direct titration of GSH, addition of KI is a prerequisite. That means iodine is formed *in situ* as an essential intermediate,

The GSH is then probably oxidized by the iodine, in a series of reaction steps, as

Interference studies : The common excipients such as starch, gum acacia, sodium chloride and common anions did not interfere in the determination of isoniazid. The amino acids, namely, leucine, valine, alanine, phenylalanine, serine, threonine, glutamine, proline, isoleucine and arginine (5 mg each) did not interfere in the direct titration of GSH (2 mg) with BAT, whereas cysteine interfered seriously. Any oxidizable species (micro level) oxidized by excess of BAT interfere in the back-titration of both INH and GSH.

It can be concluded that the present method is rapid and accurate for the determination of INH, GSH and complexes of GSH. Also number of ligand molecules present in the metal complexes of GSH could be computed easily by oxidation with BAT. Attempts to study the kinetics of GSH/INH with BAT was unsuccessful. Using fast reaction techniques, the kinetics of these reactions could be followed. Majority of the inorganic and organic substrates undergo stoichiometric oxidation around pH 4–6 by BAT. The idea in the present experimental conditions is that we are not controlling pH of the medium. Instead, the reaction is carried out in pH 5 acetate buffer medium. That means, we are not measuring the pH of the system (for the mixture). Apart from pH 4–6, non-stoichiometric oxidation occurs in other media and the same phenomenon is observed with other organic haloamines.

Experimental

Bromamine-T was prepared¹ from chloramine-T. An approximately decimolar stock solution was prepared and standardized by the iodometric method.

Recrystallized isoniazid (Koch-light), reduced glutathione (s.d. fine chem.) were used as such. INH was stand-

ardized by spectrophotometric method¹⁷. Assay of glutathione was done¹⁸. The following metal complexes of glutathione were prepared by reported methods¹⁹. (a) (glutathionato)silver(i), HOOC-CH(NH₂)-CH₂-CH₂-CONH-CH(CH₂S-Ag)CONH-CH₂-COOH, and (b) tetrakis-bis(glutathionato)cadmium(ii), Cd{Cd[OOC-CH-(NH₂)-CH₂-CH₂-CONH-CH(CH₂S)CONH-CH₂-COO H]₂}.4H₂O.

The buffer solutions were prepared according to standard methods²⁰. Hydrochloric acid, perchloric acid, sulfuric acid, sodium hydroxide, potassium iodide, sodium thiosulfate and starch (all AnalaR) were used. Solutions of the substrates (~0.01 mol dm⁻³) were prepared in the appropriate buffers as well as in triple-distilled water.

Direct titration :

Visual end-point : To an aqueous solution of GSH, starch-KI solution (~2 ml; 20% KI, 5% starch) and 1 mol dm⁻³ sulfuric acid were added to make the overall acid concentration approximately 0.02 mol dm⁻³. BAT was titrated to a permanent pale blue colour. The weight of GSH (*w*, mg) can be calculated from the relation, $w = (VN)M/n$, where *V* is the volume of titrant of normality *N* required to titrate the GSH of molecular weight *M* and *n* the number of electron change taking place.

Back-titration :

Preliminary studies : In preliminary experiments with BAT, known amount of substrate solution (~0.02 mmol) prepared in the appropriate buffer or water (acids or alkali added separately to get the overall concentration) was added to a known excessive volume of BAT solution (~2.5 mmol) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was set aside for various interval of time, with occasional shaking. Then the excess of BAT was determined by iodometric back-titration.

Recommended procedure : A sample containing substrate (~2 mg/ml) was dissolved in (a) pH 5 acetate buffer (10–15 ml) or (b) water (10–15 ml). The buffered solution was added to 0.1 mol dm⁻³ BAT solution (25 ml) or the aqueous solution was added to 0.1 mol dm⁻³ BAT solution (25 ml) containing pH 5 acetate buffer (10–15 ml). The contents were shaken for 1 min. After 15 min, 1 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ (10 ml) and 10% KI solution (20 ml) were added and the liberated iodine was titrated against 0.1 mol dm⁻³ sodium thiosulfate solution; a blank was run with BAT solution alone. The amount (*x*, mg) of the substrate, $x = (M/n) y (V_1 - V_2)$, where *M* is the molecular weight of the substrate taken, *y* the normality of thiosulfate solution, *V*₁ the volume of blank titration, *V*₂ the volume of sodium thiosulfate solution used to titrate the excess of BAT solution and *n* the number of electron change taking place.

The proposed method was employed for the determination of INH in a number of pharmaceutical preparations. At least twenty tablets of the pharmaceutical samples were

used. An appropriate amount of the pulverized sample was weighed, dissolved in water, filtered off the residue and diluted to 250 ml so that 10 ml of the solution contained 20 mg of INH (for syrup, appropriate volume was taken) Estimation was carried out by the recommended procedure (b) by taking 10 ml of the tablet solution For metal complexes of glutathione, procedure (a) was used

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